

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2020-21 academic year for MPT

ENTREPRENEURSHIP FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course

**ENTREPRENEURSHIP FOR
PHYSIOTHERAPISTS**

Duration: 30 hours (15 weeks)
(For MPT 2020 batch)

Course Objectives:

1. To provide necessary knowledge and skills required for planning, organizing & carrying out entrepreneurial activities.
2. To develop the ability of analyzing & understanding business situations.

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Course period	From December 2020 till March 2021, during 1 st semester (15 weeks)
Duration	30 hours (2 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	MPT 1 st year postgraduates (2020 batch)

Course Objectives:

1. To provide the students necessary knowledge and skills required for organizing and carrying out entrepreneurial activities.
2. To develop the ability of analyzing and understanding business situations
3. To master the knowledge necessary to plan entrepreneurial activities.

COURSE OUTLINE		
MODULE	TOPIC	HOURS
1	Theories and models of health care improvements; Theories and models of innovation and entrepreneurship for idea development and idea feasibility analysis.	7
2	Patient safety regulations; Ethics regulations.	5
3	Healthcare economics and reimbursement; Behavioural economics; Advances in digital health and health information technology.	8
4	Accelerators, incubators, and other startup resources Patents and the fundamentals of intellectual property Role of angel, seed, and venture capital investors.	6
5	Inter-professional collaboration and teamwork; Change management and Diversity.	4

Attendance Policy:

The course requires compulsory 75% attendance and only in this case a student will be issued a certificate.

References:

1. Berglund K, Verduyn K (editors). Revitalizing Entrepreneurship Education: Adopting a critical approach in the classroom. 1st ed. Routledge, 2018.
2. Bolton B, Thompson J. Entrepreneurs: Talent, Temperament and Opportunity. 3rd ed. Routledge, 2013.

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

ADAV MOHAK GIRISH (5SU20PT801)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

Handwritten signature of Dr. Sanya A in blue ink.

Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in green ink.

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

AKSHITHA K R (5SU20PT802)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

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Course Instructor

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Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

ASHWINI BHAT B (5SU20PT803)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sanya'.

Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor

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Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean

COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

ASMITA KADEL (5SU20PT804)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

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Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor

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Dr. S. Rajasekar
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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

DAYMA NIKITA OMPRAKASH (5SU20PT805)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

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Course Instructor

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

JADHAV MONALI SANJAY (5SU20PT806)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

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Course Instructor

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

JISHA V R (5SU20PT807)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

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Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor

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JOSHI JAI KAILASH (5SU20PT808)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
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Total Hours- 30

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Course Instructor

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

MOKALE PRAMOD PRABHAKAR (5SU20PT809)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

NIKITHA (5SU20PT810)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

PATEL DIVYA SANJAYBHAI (5SU20PT811)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

PATIL GANDHALI JAYKUMAR (5SU20PT812)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

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Dr. Sanya A
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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

SAROJ KUMAR SAHOO (5SU20PT813)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
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Total Hours- 30

Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor

Dr. S. Rajasekar
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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

SHETTY NIDHI SADANAND (5SU20PT814)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

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Course Instructor

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

SHINE T (5SU20PT815)

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FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

SHRAVAN KUMAR (5SU20PT816)

for successfully completing the value added course on "ENTREPRENEURSHIP
FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

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Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

SHREEJA K (5SU20PT817)

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Total Hours- 30

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CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

SOWMYA B (5SU20PT818)

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FOR PHYSIOTHERAPISTS" conducted from December 2020 to March 2021

Total Hours- 30

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